

Evaluation of granular insecticides for rainfed wetland rice in the Philippines

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Rainfed wetland rice is subject to both drought and flooding. In the Philippines, these extreme conditions influence the performance of insecticides used in controlling the key vegetative insect pests: whorl maggot, caseworm, and stem borers. Against this insect complex, foliar sprays are inferior to granular insecticide formulations because:

1. Frequent and heavy rainfall reduces the residual activity of sprays, and the need to reapply the sprays makes this form of protection more costly,
2. Larvae of the whorl maggot and stem borer are sheltered within young plants, which protect them from foliar sprays, and
3. Rainfed farmers do not have ready access to water for sprayers.

During the 1977-78 crop year, we evaluated the granular insecticides lindane, diazinon, and carbofuran, which are currently recommended in the Philippines for irrigated rice against the early-season pest complex in rainfed wetland paddies.

Diazinon and lindane granules were broadcast at 1.5 kg a.i./ha 3 days after transplanting. Carbofuran granules were incorporated into the soil at 1.0 kg a.i./ha during the last harrowing before transplanting. Previous studies have shown that soil incorporation of carbofuran was superior to broadcasting into the paddy water after transplanting.

The first trial, replicated over five farmers planted to IR28, compared lindane to carbofuran. Lindane was totally ineffective against whorl maggot and caseworm, but carbofuran controlled both pests adequately and produced significant yield increases (see table).

The second trial, replicated over seven farms planted to IR36, compared diazinon to carbofuran. Diazinon reduced whorl maggot and caseworm infestation only slightly – not enough to significantly increase yield. But carbofuran again gave excellent control and significantly higher yields.

We believe that the failure of both lindane and diazinon granules was due to the shallow paddy water, which characterizes rainfed wetland fields. We monitored the water depth daily for 30 days after transplanting. The mean depth per field ranged from 1.0 to 5.8 cm. Neither insecticide is truly systemic. Once applied to the fields the insecticides move up the plants in the capillary film between the leaf sheath and the culm. The degree of movement depends on the depth of the paddy water. In rainfed areas the paddy water is normally too shallow to allow adequate movement up the plants. Therefore lindane and diazinon should not be recommended if the paddy water levels cannot be adequately maintained.

Comparison of carbofuran, lindane, and diazinon granules for whorl maggot and caseworm control on IR28 and IR36.			
Manaoag, Pangasinan, Philippines 1977-78 ^{a/}			
		IR 28	
	Whorl maggot damage ^{b/}	Caseworm (%defoliation)	Yield (t/ha)
Insecticide	30 DT	25 DT	
Carbofuran ^{c/}	1 a	2 a	4.67 a
Lindane ^{d/}	8b	16b	3.54 b
Untreated	9b	23b	3.48 b
		IR 36	
Carbofuran ^{c/}	1 a	3a	4.43 a
Lindane ^{d/}	7b	11 b	3.99 b
Untreated	8c	15 c	3.86 b

^{a/} IR28 average of 5 fields, IR36 average of 7 fields. DT = days after transplanting. In a column any 2 means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^{b/} 1-9 scale: 1 =negligible, 9 =severe. ^{c/} 1.0 kg a.i./ha, soil incorporated. ^{d/} 1.5 kg a.i./ha, broadcast on 3 DT.

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